

Ant Colony Optimization in Cloud Computing: A Review

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Abstract— The worldwide IT industry has been greatly impacted by the cloud computing industry's explosive growth, which is expected to produce up to \$150 billion in sales by 2014, according to Gartner. With its adaptable computational architecture, cloud computing offers clients always-available services even as web technologies progress. Nonetheless, there are still issues with cost effectiveness, load balance, and energy management. Cloud providers are very concerned about energy consumption, and solutions such as virtual machine deployment have been suggested. Ant colony optimization (ACO), which provides distributed computation and robustness, stands out as a potent technique for handling challenging optimization problems in cloud computing. In cloud computing, load balancing is essential for improving resource availability and cutting costs. In order to achieve quicker reaction times, the study suggests an enhanced load balancing architecture and algorithm that makes use of ACO. Managing energy consumption and guaranteeing SLA(Service Level Agreement) compliance are difficult tasks when dealing with Virtual Machine Placement (VMP). The GACA-VMP method works well for optimizing pheromone calculations for the best physical server amount selection because it combines the advantages of genetic and ant colony algorithms. Green cloud computing prioritizes energy-efficient techniques and is essential for sustainability. The paper offers a comprehensive overview of state-of-the-art energy-efficient algorithms and offers insights into the current environment to help researchers choose the right algorithms. The study also discusses work scheduling and suggests a multi-QoS(Quality of Service)-restriction technique for effective resource balancing and QoS assurance that combines ant colony and genetic optimization. A self-adaptive ant colony optimization methodology is used to address the dynamic nature of cloud settings, exceeding earlier approaches in terms of make span and load balancing. The numerous studies' conclusions emphasized the value of bio-inspired algorithms, especially ACO, in resolving a range of cloud computing issues. These developments support continuous optimization, improving cloud computing's performance, sustainability, and affordability.

Keywords—Ant Colony Optimization, Cloud Computing, Big Data and Analytics, Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence.

I. INTRODUCTION

In order to provide speedier innovation, flexible resources, and economies of scale, cloud computing refers to the supply of computing services—including servers, storage, databases, networking, software, analytics, and intelligence—over the internet (also known as "the cloud"). Without having to make a substantial upfront investment in hardware or physical infrastructure, it enables people and organizations to access and use computer resources as needed. Some key characteristics of Cloud Computing is A) On-demand self-service, where Users don't need to communicate directly with each service provider to supply computing resources, such server instances or storage, as needed. B) Broad network access, where Cloud services are available through conventional procedures and may be accessed across a network, making them accessible to a wide range of client systems. C) Resource Pooling, where Cloud computing resources are shared across several users, with various virtual and physical resources being dynamically assigned and redistributed in response to demand. Although users might be able to choose the region in which the resources are situated, they usually have no control or knowledge over the precise placement of the resources. D) Rapid Elasticity, where Cloud computing resources may be scaled up or down to meet changing workloads since they can be provided and released quickly and elastically. E) Measured Service, Users are charged according to their utilization of cloud computing resources, which are metered and include things like storage capacity, processing power, and network bandwidth. Users may now only pay for the resources they really utilize.

Cloud Computing can be Categorized into different service Models like, 1. Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) - Scalable Computing Power, Storage. 2. Platform as a Service (PaaS) - Application Development, Database Management. 3. Software as a Service (SaaS) - Productivity Tools, Communication and Collaborations. 4. Big Data and Analytics – Data Processing,

Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence. 5. Internet of Things (IoT) - Data Collection and Processing, IoT Applications. 6. DevOps and Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) - Application Deployment

The term Cloud Security a general application of Cloud Computing which, describes the collection of guidelines, norms, practices, and technological tools used to safeguard infrastructure, data, and cloud-based systems against loss, theft, and other security risks. The key aspects of Cloud Security are, A) Data protection is the process of guaranteeing the privacy, availability, and integrity of data kept on cloud servers. To protect sensitive data, this entails putting encryption, access controls, and data loss prevention measures in place. B) Managing user identities, responsibilities, and permissions to restrict access to cloud resources is known as identity and access management, or IAM. IAM solutions make guarantee that only authorized users may access certain resources by enforcing granular access rules and authenticating users. C) Protecting the network infrastructure that links cloud resources is known as network security. To defend against unwanted access and network-based assaults, this entails putting firewalls, intrusion detection and prevention systems (IDS/IPS), and network segmentation into place. D) Governance and Compliance: Making sure that legal requirements and industry standards are followed. Cloud security protocols must be in line with industry best practices and pertinent laws. E) Threat detection and response involves keeping an eye out for possible threats, security events, and questionable activity in cloud settings. Real-time security incident detection and response are facilitated by security technologies including log management programs, Endpoint Detection and Response (EDR) platforms, and SIEM (Security Information and Event Management) systems. F) Security Automation: Using orchestration and automation technologies to automate security operations and uniformly enforce security standards in cloud settings. Automation makes it easier to find and fix security flaws, configuration errors, and compliance problems. Others are G) Cloud Provider Security, H) Incident Response and Disaster Recovery.

Generally, "Ant Colony" refers to Ant Colony Optimization (ACO), a metaheuristic optimization technique that was motivated by real ants' foraging habits. A popular method for handling a variety of computing issues is ant colony optimization, particularly in the fields of combinatorial and optimization. The way the algorithm operates is by mimicking an ant's foraging activity. In order to communicate and direct one another to food sources, real ants leave behind pheromone trails. Within the framework of ACO, virtual pheromone trails are left on the edges of a graph or solution space by artificial ants while they solve a particular optimization problem. These pheromone trails indicate which routes or solutions are desirable. The ants gravitate toward pathways with increasing concentrations of pheromones as the pheromone trails fade over time. Mostly used in Routing and Networking [Network Routing, telecommunications], Logistic and Transporation [Vehicle Routing, Supply Chain Management], Manufacturing and Production [Production Scheduling, Inventory Management], urban Planning and Traffic Management [Traffic Control, Transportation], Engineering and Design [Structural Optimization, Electronic Circuit Design].

Although cloud computing and ACO are two different ideas, they can be connected in a number of ways, particularly when it comes to optimization issues that occur in cloud computing settings. In general, ACO techniques can be used in conjunction with cloud computing to improve performance, scalability, and cost-effectiveness by offering effective solutions to optimization issues that come up in scheduling, load balancing, resource management, and network routing within cloud environments. To optimize resource usage and reduce costs in cloud computing, scheduling and resource allocation must be optimized. These optimization issues can be resolved by using ACO. In cloud computing, load balancing is dividing up incoming network traffic or workload among several servers in order to improve throughput, decrease reaction times, and guarantee optimal resource use. By allocating incoming requests and tasks to available servers in an optimal manner, ACO may be used to dynamically modify load balancing tactics. This is achieved by taking into account many parameters, including server capacity, workload, and network latency. Effective network routing is essential in cloud computing systems to guarantee dependable communication between dispersed resources and services. By identifying the best routes for data transmission, lowering latency, and decreasing network congestion, ACO may be used to improve network routing decisions. Determining the best location for services or Virtual Machines (VMs) and moving them across various cloud providers or regions may be a challenging optimization task in multi-cloud or hybrid cloud settings. ACO techniques take into account many parameters including latency, cost, and availability of resources across several cloud environments to identify near-optimal solutions for service placement and migration.

Comparative Study

Sl. No	Title	Author name	Description	Limitations
1	Energy Efficient Data Center in Cloud Computing	Vikram Yadav, Pooja Malik, Adarsh Kumar	In fact, Gartner estimated that the global cloud computing market would bring in almost \$150 billion in sales by 2014. Still , the worldwide market in 2011 is valued at more than \$68 billion.It's been observed tha t when online and internet technologies adv	In conclusion, our concerted efforts in devising an ecologically responsible data center design for cloud infrastructure as a service (IaaS) revolve around the introduction of the innovative PCTN (Power Node for Tuning Consumption) module. The culmination of our research is

			<p>ance, cloud computing technologies follow suit. Cloud computing is an incredibly strong and flexible computational architecture that offers clients always available services. Software is no longer limited to a particular hardware environment and is employed in accordance with the resource pool's schedule for maximum resource consumption. A resource pool is built by merging different hardware and software resources. Optimizing energy consumption in the cloud computing environment is the difficulty of allocating resources efficiently while applying various energy saving strategies. It is possible for various resources to be needed at different times in a cloud environment.</p> <p>It has been observed that maintaining QoS (Quality of Service) in the cloud requires effective load control.</p> <p>The tasks on an overloaded physical machine are transferred to an underloaded physical machine, and the idle machine is turned off, in order to create green cloud. Power Nap and DVFS are two useful strategies for energy optimization.</p> <p>Much of this energy is wasted by dormant systems; in most deployments, even with server utilization below 30%, idle servers still consume 60% of their peak power. In this work, we have introduced an energy optimization method that considers both SLA and QoS requirements</p>	<p>visually presented through a comprehensive flow diagram elucidating the intricate nexus between the PCPM and the Controller node. This governing nexus, in turn, orchestrates the meticulous regulation of power consumption within the data center by harnessing the functionalities of diverse modules such as TVM, VM, EM, QoS, SA, VMTD, and more. The synergistic interplay of these diverse components operates in unison to not only optimize power utilization but also underscore our commitment to advancing environmental sustainability within the dynamic landscape of cloud computing. This holistic approach, encapsulated in the graphical representation, signifies a pivotal stride towards aligning the escalating demand for computational resources with a conscientious imperative to minimize the ecological footprint. As we navigate the trajectory of cloud technology evolution, embracing such environmentally conscious practices emerges as imperative for nurturing a sustainable and responsible digital ecosystem.</p>
2	<p>A Performed Load Balancing Algorithm for Public Cloud Computing Using Ant Colony Optimization</p>	<p>Awatif Ragmani, Amina EI Omri, Noreddine Abghour, Khalid Moussaid, Mohammed Rida</p>	<p>In just a few short of years, cloud computing has grown remarkably. In fact, the economic model it employs, which bases hardware and software demand on technical factors like memory, bandwidth, and usage, or package, has made a significant contribution to the global liberalization of computer resources.</p> <p>However, to maintain a high degree of security, availability, and responsiveness, Cloud providers must optimize the performance of the many services they offer in order to further improve Cloud computing.</p> <p>Load balancing is a key component in addressing performance difficulties in cloud computing. In actuality, effective load balancing maximizes resource availability while reducing expenses.</p> <p>In this work, we examine several studies that have addressed load balancing in cloud computing. In order to provide a faster reaction time, we further suggest an enhanced load b</p>	<p>With more people using the cloud and more data centers spread out across more geographic areas, it's getting more and harder to keep up acceptable levels of availability and security and responsiveness using load balancing in traditional models 01'. In this research, we suggest an improved load balancing architecture by providing a two-part sharing of functions 01', the main controller that represents the cloud entry point.</p> <p>First, the primary controller will continue to divide up user tasks across several regional load balancers using function 01'. Second, using a variety of agents, the auxiliary controller will guarantee that the system is updated. If not, we decide to combine many techniques to optimize the mapping and partitioning processes.</p> <p>In a nutshell, the three layers of the proposed architecture 01' the Cloud are assigned distinct roles</p>

			<p>balancing architecture and algorithm for cloud computing.</p>	<p>and algorithms. To select the most efficient load balancer, the main controller uses an algorithm based on the geographic location of both the user and the data center. To assign the proper nodes to users' work, the regional load balancer implements a second policy based on the ant colony optimization algorithm. Our goal with this strategy is to optimize all of the cloud's response times of services. After this effort, we want to evaluate the suggested solutions in two different settings: first, on the CloudSim simulator, and then in real life. Lastly, we want to refine the suggested algorithm.</p>
3	<p>An Energy-Aware Ant Colony Algorithm for Network-Aware Virtual Machine Placement in Cloud Computing</p>	<p>Chuangen Gao, Hua Wang, Linbo Zhai, Yanqing Gao, Shanwen Yi</p>	<p>One of the main issues facing cloud providers is the cost of energy. It has been shown that virtual machine deployment is a successful strategy for reducing energy use. Since virtual machines are not isolated and need to communicate with one another in order to exchange data, constraints imposed by network resources, such as bandwidth, are as important as those imposed by physical machine resources, such as CPU and memory (PM-constraints). But server resources are the only focus of the majority of recent data center power optimization research. Due to the possibility of traffic congestion and decreased network performance resulting from server consolidation without network consideration, the optimization outcomes are frequently subpar. We outline the virtual machine placement problem under both PM-constraints and Net-constraints to minimize the energy cost, taking into account the traffic demands between virtual machines. We then provide an ant colony optimization-based solution to address the problem. We use a simulation study to assess the predicted performance of our suggested method, and the results clearly show that our suggested approach is superior.</p>	<p>The deployment of virtual machines in cloud computing network infrastructures was examined in this paper. We take traffic demands between virtual machines into account and describe the virtual machine placement problem under both PM-constraints and Net-constraints because virtual machines are not isolated and communicate with one another to exchange data. In order for the ants to identify the way that satisfies the traffic demands, we then suggested a method based on ant colony optimization to address the problem and develop the heuristic information linked with network resource factor for the first time. Ultimately, simulation results demonstrate that our method performs better in terms of reject rate and power usage.</p>

4	Cloud-Computing-Based Resource Allocation Research on the Perspective of Improved Ant Colony Algorithm	Junjun XU, Weihua HU, Ke LI, Qian BAO	Ant colony algorithm (ACO) is a novel intelligent optimization technique with distributed computing, positive feedback, and strong robustness. It is effective at resolving challenging combinational optimization issues. A single ACO does, however, have a number of defections, including a slow primary stage solving speed, poor convergence precision, and an easy tendency to settle on a local optimal solution. The study that was presented leveraged the fast-searching capability of genetic algorithms (GA) in conjunction with ACO to compensate for the initial pheromone deficit and accelerate ACO convergence. The simulation tool MATLAB's experimental result shows that the ACO is a more efficient method of solving resource allocation problems than the classic GA.	The article that was presented examined how resources are allocated in a cloud computing environment and examined the effectiveness of genetic and ant colony algorithms. The presented paper proposed a new resource allocation algorithm that uses a dynamic pheromone updating strategy and introduces the system transition probability to make the algorithm more effective at the next node. This was achieved by integrating the two algorithms to make up for their respective shortcomings. It was discovered through a MATLAB simulation experiment that the integrated algorithm is a more efficient resource allocation method than the conventional ACO.
5	Deadline Constrained Cloud Computing Resources Scheduling through an Ant Colony System Approach	Zong-Gan Chen, Zhi-Hui Zhan, Hai-Hao Li, Ke-Jing Du, Jing-Hui Zhong, Yong Wee Foo, Yun Li, Jun Zhang	Because scheduling cloud computing resources affects both execution time and execution cost, it is crucial for carrying out workflows in the cloud platform. We have devised an effective solution based on the ant colony system (ACS) to meet deadline limitations while optimizing execution costs. An ant in ACS is a solution with T dimensions for scheduling T tasks on R resources. Each dimension has a task as its value, and each dimension's value is an integer range in [1, R] to indicate which resource the job should be scheduled on. By using this type of solution encoding, the ant in ACS builds a solution in T steps, choosing one resource from the R resources in an optimal manner for each step based on heuristic and pheromone data. As a result, to represent the mapping relation of activities and resources, the solution encoding is quite straightforward and easy to understand. Furthermore, it makes perfect sense to use the solution construct process to identify the best solution given the encoding scheme. We have carried out a number of in-depth studies using different cloud resources and workflows at different scales. We contrast the outcomes with those obtained using the dynamic objective genetic algorithm (DOGA) and particle swarm optimization (PSO) techniques. The experimental findings demonstrate that, under a variety of scheduling scales and deadline conditions, ACS can identify better solutions at a cheaper cost than both PSO and DOGA.	In this research, we have devised a cost-minimization and deadline-constrained model-based approach to the cloud computing resource scheduling problem using ant colony systems. The model can satisfy the demands of corporate organizations and is freely available. The shortcomings of this model that the PSO and DOGA techniques encountered have been fixed. The studies conducted with different scheduling scales and deadline restrictions demonstrate that the ACS can find a better solution than PSO and DOGA with a smaller TEC. Future research will focus on improving the ACS's stability while investigating the use of various evolutionary computation techniques, including upgraded PSOs, artificial bee colonies, differential evolution, and brain storm optimization. Additionally, utilizing pertinent algorithms, dynamic and multi-objective aspects will be examined.

6	Energy Efficient Algorithms based on VM Consolidation for Cloud Computing	Qiheng Zhou, Minxian Xu, Sukhpal Singh Gill, Chengxi Gao, Wenhong Tian, Chengzhong Xu, and Rajkumar Buyya	<p>The concept of cloud computing has transformed the IT sector and made computing available as the fifth utility. The pay-as-you-go approach of cloud computing makes it possible to provide consumers with resources on-demand.</p> <p>Cloud computing is gaining interest from both academics and businesses, with many seeing it as the foundation of the modern economy. However, cloud data centers' high energy consumption raises operating expenses and releases carbon emissions into the atmosphere.</p> <p>Thus, in order to guarantee sustainability and energy efficiency, green cloud computing is necessary, and this may be done by using energy-efficient methods. Using energy-efficient algorithms to maximize resource utilization and energy consumption is one of the popular strategies. To lower the energy consumption of cloud computing environments, a number of energy-efficient strategies based on virtual machine consolidation have now been developed. But the majority of them aren't thoroughly compared in the same conditions, and their effectiveness isn't assessed in the same experimental conditions. This makes it difficult for users to choose the best algorithm for their goals. In this work, we thoroughly examine a number of cutting-edge energy-efficient algorithms from a variety of angles, including architecture, modeling, and metrics, in order to offer insights into current energy-efficient algorithms and assist researchers in selecting the most appropriate algorithm.</p> <p>Furthermore, we employ the CloudSimtools to develop and assess these algorithms using identical experimental parameters. The comparative performance analysis of various algorithms with complete outcomes is demonstrated by the experimental results.</p>	<p>Our research into five cutting-edge, energy-efficient methods for cloud data centers that are based on virtual machine consolidations is presented in this publication. From several angles, including fundamental concepts, designs, modeling, and algorithm complexity, we examine and contrast the algorithms. As mentioned in these algorithms, we also apply these techniques to CloudSim and set up the parameters accordingly. Experiments under synthetic and real tracing conditions yielded findings that demonstrate these algorithms' ability to effectively minimize energy usage while balancing energy's trade offs with other metrics, including SLA violations and VM migrations. Our analysis has led us to identify the following next research directions:</p> <p>The self-adaptive threshold configuration approach can be further researched because utilization threshold settings have a significant impact on energy usage. The majority of energy-efficient algorithms based on virtual machine consolidation view the CPU resource as the bottleneck and the primary component of their power models. It is possible to take into account resource usage and energy consumption in relation to other resources, such as networks. Meta-heuristic algorithms have demonstrated superior performance in terms of energy conservation when compared to regular heuristic algorithms. Nevertheless, a reduction in the solution space can help minimize the associated time cost.</p>
7	Virtual Machine Placement Scheduling in Cloud Computing	Liang Hong, Ge Yufei	<p>Cloud computing leverages virtualization technologies to offer resources to clients as services. One of the key concerns when it comes to h</p>	<p>Ant placement between VM pairs describes how the method optimizes the pheromone calculation in load balancing theory by</p>

	<p>Based on Genetic Ant Colony Algorithm Approach</p>		<p>osting virtual machines (VMs) on physical servers appears to be how middle-class and industrializing nations will manage the significant energy consumption associated with data center server maintenance. As a result, the VM placement (VMP) issue is important for cloud computing and energy optimization. In this work, we present GACA-VMP, a heuristic method for solving the VMP problem that is based on an enhanced ant colony algorithm (ACA). The letter G stands for genetic, indicating that the algorithm will work in tandem with the genetic algorithm to solve the issue. The algorithm optimizes the pheromone calculation in load balancing theory by evaluating the pheromone during the ant motions, which is described in ant placement between VM pairs. This allows us to choose the appropriate selection outcomes. We compare the results of the first-fit decreasing (FFD) method and the simple ant colony algorithm (ACA) with the suggested GACAVMP approach's performance in solving VMP. The outcomes demonstrate that GACAVMP can solve VMP more effectively while utilizing exceptional resource efficiency to choose the ideal quantity of physical servers.</p>	<p>analyzing the pheromone during the ant motions. This enables us to select the proper selection results. We evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed GACAVMP strategy in solving VMP against the outcomes of the first-fit decreasing (FFD) method and the simple ant colony algorithm (ACA). The results show that GACA-VMP can select the optimal number of physical servers while solving VMP more efficiently and with outstanding resource efficiency, showing that our approach is competitive, particularly given the high number of virtual machines. The GACA-VMP policy is presently implemented in a cloud environment that is uniform. Our goal is to migrate this to a true cloud platform like OpenStack1 and a diverse cloud environment. In order to make the cloud and green computing truly helpful in solving the source management issue, we will also test a few apps there.</p>
<p>8</p>	<p>Local Search Based Ant Colony Optimization for Scheduling in Cloud Computing</p>	<p>Naveen Kumar Gondhi, Aditya Sharma</p>	<p>Cloud computing has emerged as the most promising area of the computing environment in recent years. Its appealing qualities and technological improvements are causing an increasing number of enterprises to use it on a daily basis. This work presents a modified strategy that utilizes the ant colony optimization algorithm to optimize the allocation process of virtual machines to their corresponding physical counterparts. This can significantly improve how well the present physical resources are used.</p>	<p>This study views the scheduling of virtual machine allocation to real machines as a combinatorial bin packing problem. Given that bin packing is an NP-hard problem, an approximation technique must be used to obtain a solution in a finite amount of time. We suggest using an ant colony optimization approach that was bioinspired and then further altered by incorporating a local search strategy. Better outcomes were attained and the degree of optimization was further increased. The current method only yields one optimal solution at the end; however, it can be improved to yield a list of several alternatives, such that following a few migrations, a list of solutions ranked by decreasing</p>

				efficiency is available to be selected as the subsequent optimal solution.
9	Multi-Population Ant Colony Algorithm for Virtual Machine Deployment	Xuemei Sun, Kai Zhang, Maode Ma, Hua Su	Since cloud computing technology has been developing so quickly lately, it's become crucial to figure out how to efficiently lower cloud data center prices. The primary goal of the research on virtual machine deployment is to logically and efficiently allocate virtual machine resources needed by users on a real server. This research suggests an algorithm for multi-population ant colonies to address virtual machine deployment issues. This algorithm uses multiple ant colonies for the solution, with resource wastage and energy consumption as optimization objectives. It determines strategies for information exchange among ant colonies based on the information entropy of each population to ensure the balance of its convergence and diversity. The simulation results demonstrate that this method outperforms the single-population ant colony algorithm in terms of performance and may effectively minimize energy consumption and resource waste for high-demand virtual machine deployments.	The paper proposes a multi-population ant colony algorithm to efficiently deploy virtual machines on physical servers. The algorithm optimizes resource wastage and energy consumption by using multiple ant colonies and determining information exchange strategies based on each population's entropy. Simulation results show this algorithm outperforms the single-population ant colony algorithm for high-demand virtual machine deployment. Future research should focus on execution efficiency, execution time reduction, load balancing, and network bandwidth to adapt to technological advancements in data centers.
10	An Energy Efficient Ant Colony System for Virtual Machine Placement in Cloud Computing	Xiao-Fang Liu, Zhi-Hui Zhan, Jeremiah D. Deng, Yun Li, Tianlong Gu, Jun Zhang	Energy efficiency and virtual machine placement (VMP) are important areas of study in cloud computing. In order to schedule unused servers and reduce the number of active physical servers, evolutionary computing is applied to VMP in this article in order to conserve energy. An ACS-based strategy is created to accomplish the VMP aim, motivated by the algorithm's promising performance for combinatorial problems (the ant colony system, or ACS). The resulting algorithm is known as an OEMACS when it is combined with order exchange and migration (OEM) local search approaches. From the standpoint of global optimization, it successfully reduces the number of active servers that are utilized to assign virtual machines (VMs) by using a revolutionary pheromone deposition approach that directs artificial ants toward viable solutions that cluster candidate VMs together. The OEMACS is used in cloud environments with both homogeneous and heterogeneous servers for a range of VMP challenges with varying VM sizes. The findings demonstrate that the OEMACS provides notable energy savings and more effective utilization of various resources while typically outperforming alternative evolutionary-based methods and traditional heuristics, particularly on VMP with	The paper presents an energy-efficient approach to the VMP problem in cloud computing, focusing on optimizing virtual machine (VM) deployment with minimal active servers and switching off idle ones. The approach uses artificial ants to assign VMs based on global search information, distributing pheromone between VM pairs and learning from historical experience. Local search is performed to revise infeasible solutions and speed up global convergence. The number of servers for placing VMs reduces as the generation number grows, avoiding computation waste and providing guidance for further advancement. The OEMACS is efficient for large-scale problems and is applied to various cloud systems. Experimental results show that it minimizes active servers, improves resource utilization, balances resources, and reduces power consumption. The performance of OEMACS is not sensitive to parameters, making it more competitive.

			bottleneck resource characteristics.	
11	Network energy consumption analysis and dormancy mechanism based on ant colony algorithm in cloud computing environment for IOT service and real-time embedded industrial control system	Shi Shaoling, Zhang Jing, Chen Moliang, Rong Hui, Cui Yi, Fu Xiaodong	Cloud computing issues have long been a hot topic in both business and academic study. Currently, cloud computing technology is widely employed in IOT (Internet of Things) services and real-time embedded industrial control system energy consumption. This study examines how much energy each piece of equipment uses in a cloud computing environment when it is in the dormant state. In the meanwhile, a novel model for the optimization of energy consumption is constructed in this research by incorporating the ant colony algorithm into a fundamental network energy consumption model. The cloud computing simulation platform CLOUDSIM was used to carry out the simulation trials. This paper's model was shown to be more efficient and effective when compared to two other algorithms: Dijkstra and Min LP.	In order to provide IOT (Internet of Things) services, this article examines the energy consumption of the network model and the dormancy mechanism in the cloud computing environment. embedded, real-time industrial control system. Additionally, this research proposes an energy optimization model of the dormancy mechanism based on the ant colony algorithm. The system uses the benefits of the ant colony algorithm to enable every device to determine its lowest energy consumption status within the effective period without interfering with regular operation. Additionally, the data were examined using the Dijkstra, ant colony, and Min LP algorithms at various stages. However, the analysis on the experimental results in this paper proves that energy consumption model of dormancy mechanism based on ant colony algorithm can better optimize and improve the impact of delay. For example, when $\theta = 0.60$ in the model, the energy consumption is reduced to 46.5%, and the delay was only 4.3%.
12	A Multi-Objective Ant Colony System Algorithm for Virtual Machine Placement in Traffic Intense Data Centers	Yao Qin, Hua Wang, Fangjin Zhu, Linbo Zhai	The VM placement issue for cloud applications requiring a lot of bandwidth is examined in this study. Prior research focuses on network communications income and identifying the most suitable virtual machines (VMs); nevertheless, it frequently ignores the placement of the chosen VMs, resulting in excessive power usage. The purpose of the study is to solve this problem and enhance data center performance. We express the issue as a rigorously NP-hard bin packing problem. Next, we provide ACS-BVMP, a multiobjective Ant Colony System (ACS) Algorithm. The objective is to determine the Pareto optimum solution set, which may increase communications income and decrease PM power usage at the same time. Some examples from the literature are used to test the suggested algorithm. It's Three single-objective algorithms and two multi-objective algorithms currently in use are compared to the solution set. Our suggested approach works better than the previous algorithms, according to the findings.	The number of cloud applications, such as SAN, which have high bandwidth needs, has increased significantly in recent years due to the popularity of cloud computing. In this work, We suggest the ACSBVMP multi-objective ACS method for solving the VM placement issue in bandwidth-intensive applications. Our objective is to enhance communication income while minimizing PM power use. Examples from the literature are used to test the suggested method. Our suggested approach performs better in terms of ONVG, SP, and power saving than two other multi-objective algorithms. Next, we evaluate it against three single-objective methods for each of the objectives. According to the comparison, ACS-BVMP performs better than other algorithms. Finally, we verify the scalability of the proposed algorithm through several experiments.
13	GACA-VMP: Virtual Machine Placement Scheduling in Cloud Computing Based on Genetic Ant Colony Algorithm	Liang Hong, Ge Yufei	In this paper we propose a heuristic approach based on an improved ant colony algorithm (ACA) to solve the VMP problem, named as GACA-VMP. G is displayed for genetics, which indicates that the problem will be solved by the algorithm working in tandem with the genetic	The paper proposes a genetic ant colony algorithm for consolidating virtual machines (VMs) on servers in cloud computing environments. The algorithm aims to minimize total resources and maximize server utilization. The performance is compared to simple ACA and a first-fit decreasing algorithm, showing its

	Approach		algorithm. The method optimizes the pheromone calculation in load balancing theory by evaluating the pheromone during the ant motions, which is described in ant placement between VM pairs. This allows us to choose the appropriate selection outcomes. We compare the results of the first-fit decreasing (FFD) method and the basic ant colony algorithm (ACA) with the suggested GACAVMP approach's performance in solving VMP. The outcomes demonstrate that GACA-VMP can solve VMP more effectively while utilizing exceptional resource efficiency to choose the ideal quantity of physical servers.	competitiveness, especially for large VM numbers. The GACA-VMP policy is currently deployed in a homogeneous cloud environment, but is being moved to heterogeneous environments and real cloud platforms like OpenStack.
14	A Virtual Machine Consolidation Algorithm Based on Ant Colony System and Extreme Learning Machine for Cloud Data Center	Fagui Liu, Zhenjiang Ma, Bin Wang, Weiwei Lin	The energy consumption issue in large-scale data centers is a growing concern, and virtual machine consolidation can help reduce it. However, excessive consolidation can lead to Service Level Agreement (SLA) violations. To balance effective energy consumption and SLA violations avoidance, a lower complexity multi-population ant colony system algorithm is proposed. The algorithm uses Extreme Learning Machine (ELM) prediction to predict host states, migrate overloaded virtual machines to normal hosts, and consolidate underloaded ones to higher utilization hosts. Multiple populations construct migration plans and local search optimizes results to reduce SLA violations. Experimental results show that the algorithm effectively reduces energy consumption, migration times, and SLA violations compared to other algorithms.	This paper proposes a virtual machine consolidation algorithm using ELM and ACS. Multiple ELM models predict host state, while multi-population ACS algorithms reduce search space. Underloaded and overloaded hosts are analyzed, and heuristic information and migration rules are designed. In order to prove the advancement of our proposed ELM_MPACS, we compared it with other seven algorithms of IQR_MMT_1.5, THR_MMT_0.8, MAD_MMT_2.5, LR_MMT_1.2, MSE_MMT_4.0, ACS_VMC and ST_MPACS on the CloudSim platform. We concluded that The ELM prediction algorithm accurately predicts host state in next scheduling cycles, avoiding unnecessary migrations and reducing SLA violations. The local search algorithm optimizes solutions, balances loads, and reduces violations. The pheromone exchange between populations increases the likelihood of selecting the best solution, reducing energy consumption, migration times, and SLA violations. The algorithm is aimed at real-world data centers for further energy efficiency.
15	A Task Scheduling Algorithm Based on Genetic Algorithm and Ant Colony Optimization Algorithm with Multi-QoS Constraints in Cloud Computing	Yangyang Dai, Yuansheng Lou, Xin Lu	In a cloud computing context, task scheduling is an NP-hard issue with a challenging to find precise optimal solution that may be addressed using intelligent optimization techniques to get close to the ideal outcome. Quality of service (QoS) is a crucial metric to assess how well task scheduling is working in the interim. This work proposes a unique task scheduling method, MQoS-GAAC, with multi-QoS restrictions, taking into account the scheduling process's time-consuming, expensive, secure, and reliable aspects. The algorithm combines the genetic algorithm (GA) with the ant colony optimization algorithm (ACO). GA is triggered in order to efficiently produce the first pheromone	The task scheduling method MQoS-GAAC, which takes into account several QoS requirements and combines ACO and GA, is proposed in this study. By merging ACO with GA and transforming QoS into GA membership features, fitness function, we may determine that the best scheduling plan satisfies user service requirements. Simulation findings using the CloudSim platform demonstrate that this approach greatly improves QoS and outperforms ACO and GA in terms of time span and resource load balancing. The following stage will take into account more detailed QoS parameters and dynamically modify the algorithm's associated parameters.

			for ACO. The evaluation of 4-dimensional QoS targets is done using the proposed fitness function. Then, ACO is utilized to seek out the optimum resource. The experiment indicates that the proposed algorithm has preferable performance both in balancing resources and guaranteeing QoS.	
16	SAACO: A Self Adaptive Ant Colony Optimization in Cloud Computing	Weifeng Sun, Zhenxing Ji, Jianli Sun, Ning Zhang, Yan Hu	The cloud environment is complicated, dynamic, and diversified. The robustness and self-organization of Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) flexibility, which is absolutely right for the cloud environment. The ACO method, which mimics ant foraging, is useful for solving issues when the best answer is sought for. In cloud computing, work scheduling is another issue for which an ideal solution is sought after. A self-adaptive ant colony optimization (SAACO) is suggested in this study. We employ particle swarm optimization (PSO) in SAACO to make the ACO parameters self-adaptive in order to address some of the drawbacks of the PACO that we previously presented, such as parameter selection and pheromone updating. Additionally, we enhance the pheromone's computation and updating. The findings demonstrate that SAACO outperforms PACO in terms of makespan and load balancing.	This research proposes a self-adaptive ant colony optimization for scheduling activities in cloud computing. Based on the ACO parameters' self-adaptability and the updated method for SAACO performs well when the pheromone is updated and computed. The results of the simulation studies show that SAACO outperforms PACO, which we previously presented, in terms of both makespan and load balance. In this work, we verify that SAACO can achieve good scheduling performance for cloud computing activities. To boost the performance, there are a few specifics, nevertheless, that we need focus on. The primary issue is that we utilize the standard value for the PSO-part parameters in SAACO rather than giving them careful thought. We plan to do further study on this topic in the future.
17	An Improved Ant Colony Optimization Algorithm for Improving Cloud Resource Utilization	NIE Qingbin, LI Pinghua	Improved Ant Colony Optimization (IACO) is a technique intended to increase cloud computing utilization efficiency. This improvement is made by creatively enhancing both inspired elements and pheromone factors, expanding on the Capabilities of already existing algorithms in the sector. Specifically, dynamic adaptability is made possible by the modifications made to pheromone components, which allow the algorithm to react to changes in the cloud environment efficiently. Additionally, inspired elements are improved, giving artificial ants more precise direction when making decisions. Emulation tests are carried out in CloudSim, a cloud computing simulation environment, in order to verify the effectiveness of the suggested IACO algorithm. According to the test results, IACO outperforms both the most recent Improved Artificial Bee Colony (IABC) algorithms and traditional Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) Algorithms in terms of task execution efficiency. The current IABC and traditional ACO must be compared since it identifies particular si	The efficiency with which computer resources, such as CPU, memory, and storage, are being used is gauged by a cloud system's resource utilization rate. It illustrates how best resource allocation is balanced with the ever-changing needs of activities and applications. Efficient use of available resources is indicated by a high resource utilization rate, and this is important for cloud settings because it affects both performance and cost. The rates at which resources are utilized are largely determined by effective load balancing and dynamic scaling methods. In order to avoid resource bottlenecks and maximize system performance, load balancing makes sure, that workloads are dispersed equally. Through dynamic scaling, the cloud system can balance cost-effectiveness and efficiency by modifying resource distribution in response to current demands. The improvements made to the

			tuations or circumstances in which IACO performs exceptionally well. This comparison highlights how resilient and flexible IACO is in various cloud computing scenarios. The overall conclusion highlights the role that IACO plays in optimizing cloud resource consumption, which can result in possible cost savings and improved system performance in practical implementations.	Improved Ant Colony Optimization (IACO) algorithm help artificial ants make more intelligent decisions, which may result in more efficient work distribution and resource use. This is especially important given how scalable and dynamic cloud infrastructures are. In addition to improving operational effectiveness, aiming for a high resource utilization rate also helps achieve sustainability objectives by lowering environmental impact and energy usage. Thus, techniques and algorithms that improve cloud computing resource utilization is essential to maintaining the efficient and long-lasting operation of these intricate infrastructures.
18	Osmotic Bio-Inspired Load Balancing Algorithm in Cloud Computing.	Marwa Gamal, Rawya Rizk, Hani Mahdi, Basem E. Elnaghi.	This paper's primary objective is to present a hybrid metaheuristics approach that blends bio-inspired load balancing algorithms with osmotic behavior. Virtual machines (VMs) can be automatically deployed and transferred through cloud infrastructures thanks to the osmotic behavior. The paper then takes advantage of these bio-inspired algorithms to form an osmotic hybrid artificial bee colony and ant colony (OH_BAC) optimization load balancing algorithm, since the hybrid artificial bee colony and ant colony optimization proved its efficiency in the dynamic environment in cloud computing.	This work proposes to use the chemical theory of osmosis to develop osmotic computing and identify load balancing for virtual machine placement using the OH_BAC method. To create an energy-efficient cloud computing environment, OH_BAC uses the osmosis approach. ACO and ABC work together in the OH_BAC algorithm to choose the ideal VM to migrate to the most appropriate PM. Furthermore, OH_BAC reduces power usage by activating the most appropriate osmotic host out of all the PMs in the system. In two trials with fixed and changing loads, the suggested method has been simulated to determine the performance at various metrics. ACO, ABC, H_BAC, and host overloading detection techniques are compared with the OH_BAC algorithm.
19	Improving the Response Time of M-Learning and Cloud Computing Environments Using a Dominant Firefly Approach.	Kaushik Sekaran, Mohammad S. Khan, Rizwan Patan, Amir H. Gandomi, Parimala Venkata Krishna, Suresh Kallam.	Heavy traffic or uneven loads at the cloud data centers and related cloud servers are typically the result of requests from different terminals made by cloud users. Therefore, each cloud server needs a cloud load balancer that employs an effective load balancing mechanism. We present the dominating firefly method, a novel meta-heuristic algorithm that maximizes job load balancing across the several virtual machines in the cloud server. This increases the response efficiency of the cloud servers, which in turn improves the accuracy of m-learning systems.	In order to enhance job load balancing in the cloud computing environment, the suggested dominating firefly behavior search model was implemented and simulated in CSVM instances in this work. Throughput and reaction time are two examples of QoS measurements that are increased in this way, which aids in balancing the load across numerous CSVMs. Additionally, our solutions optimize the workload of job requests that Cloud end-users send to CSVMs in order to boost the Cloud server's efficiency.
20	Energy Efficient Virtual Machine Placement With	Wenting Wei, Huaxi Gu, Wanyun Lu,	Our goal in this paper was to lower power consumption and communication costs over traffic-aware data center networks by	This work proposes an approach called E2VMP to handle the energy-efficient VMP problem. It uses ant colony optimization to tackle the VMP

	an Improved Ant Colony Optimization Over Data Center Networks.	Tong Zhou, Xuanzhang Liu.	proposing an energy-efficient virtual machine deployment technique. An enhanced approach using adaptive parameter setting was provided to address this type of optimization problem, balancing the ant colony's robust search capabilities with quick convergence.	problem and formulates it as a bi-objective optimization problem. To discover the optimal placement option, we enhance the ant colony optimization algorithm, known as AP-ACO, with the goal of achieving quick convergence and robust search capacity. Our suggested scheme's performance is assessed in relation to the Random and FFD algorithms.
21	Defending Against Co-Residence Attack in Energy-Efficient Cloud: An Optimization Based Real-Time Secure VM Allocation Strategy.	Lu Cao, Ruiwen Li, Xiaojun Ruan, Yuhong Liu.	In this paper, we propose a safe, workload-balanced, and energy-efficient virtual machine allocation technique to thwart such co-residence attacks. To be more precise, we formulate the issue as an optimization problem and quantify and minimize three main factors: (1) power consumption, (2) security threats, and (3) uneven workloads across several physical servers. Additionally, this work assumes a random number of virtual machines (VMs) from various users coming at random times to take into account a genuine environmental situation.	A safe, workload-balanced, and energy-efficient virtual machine allocation technique was our suggested countermeasure against such co-residence attacks. It utilized an optimization model to represent the virtual machine allocation problem. Using the Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) algorithm—an evolutionary algorithm modeled after the actions of natural ants—we were able to determine the best allocation approach because the optimization problem is NP-hard.
22	Efficient Task Offloading for IoT-Based Applications in Fog Computing Using Ant Colony Optimization.	Mohamed K. Hussein, Mohamed H. Mousa.	This paper proposes two distinct scheduling algorithms to efficiently load balance IoT tasks over the fog nodes while taking communication cost and response time into account. The two nature-inspired meta-heuristic schedulers used are ant colony optimization (ACO) and particle swarm optimization (PSO). The round robin (RR) algorithm's experimental results are contrasted with those of the suggested algorithms.	The scenario of a smart city, where a large number of dispersed IoT sensors generate a big amount of data that must be processed in order to make decisions and carry out coordinated actions, serves as the inspiration for this study. In the context of smart cities, fog computing is portrayed as crucial because it allows Internet of Things (IoT) apps to benefit from lower latencies by utilizing fog computing instead of the cloud for processing, thereby improving reaction times for these apps. On the fog nodes, an IoT task offloading formal model is given. The fog nodes' service rate and network latency are taken into account in the formal model.
23	A Hybrid Model for Load Balancing in Cloud Using File Type Formatting.	Muhammad Junaid, Adnan Sohail, Adeel Ahmed, Abdullah Baz, Imran Ali Khan, Hosam Alhakami.	A new hybrid model is being developed that uses file type formatting to classify the number of files in the cloud in order to give a better load balancing solution for cloud computing with large amounts of data. Support Vector Machine (SVM) is used to classify data, taking into account a variety of file types including text maps, audio, video, and cloud-based images. For improved load balancing in the cloud, the produced data class's high classification accuracy is put into a metaheuristic algorithm called Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) that uses File Type Formatting (FTF).	This study has performed file format classifications in cloud computing, which is a novel contribution to the field of classification. To the best of the authors' knowledge, there hasn't been any file format classification done in cloud computing literature. The work has had a big influence on looking into a new field for cloud research. Two steps of a hybrid strategy have been developed by the conducted investigation. The first step involves changing SVM to accurately classify a first 100,000 file formats, including text, video, audio, and images. Because datasets and file types vary in size, processing times also do.
24	Virtual Machine Placement Optimization for Big Data Applications in	Seyyed Mohsen Seyyedsalehi, Mohammad Khansari,	A novel method for placing virtual machines (VMs) in a multi-data center (DC) cloud environment is presented in this research. Context-aware algorithms like aware genetic algorithm first fit (AGAFF)	Many areas of computing have altered since cloud computing first emerged. High-level technologies including big data, edge computing, IoT, and artificial intelligence are supported by this cost-effective and dynamic platform. Global

	Cloud Computing.		use a framework to reduce traffic between MapReduce nodes and can identify large data tasks based on an input tag. The foundation of this multi-objective algorithm is the genetic algorithm, which is integrated with the first fit methodology. The approach maximizes pertinent CPU and RAM consumption in each server while decreasing the number of used servers, intra-DC traffic of large data operations, and live migration of virtual machines.	warming, large-scale energy use, and CO2 emissions are some of the problems that its expansion may bring. In order to minimize the negative consequences of cloud computing by optimizing the placement of virtual machines, numerous researchers have concentrated on related topics. Reducing energy consumption and promoting green computing can be accomplished by offering different options for placing desired virtual machines (VMs) in the best possible way.
25	Enhancement of Health Care Services Based on Cloud Computing in IOT Environment Using Hybrid Swarm Intelligence.	Karim M. Hassan, A. Abdo, Ahmed Yakoub.	In the context of the Internet of Things, this research suggests a novel approach to enhance work scheduling in healthcare services using cloud computing (cloud-IoT). In particular, the advantages of particle swarm optimization (PSO) and the Salp Swarm Algorithm (SSA) are integrated in the hybrid optimization algorithm HPSOSSA, which integrates the best swarm intelligence algorithms currently in use.	As a component of an intelligent model, this research introduced the meta-heuristic hybrid particle swarm optimization and salp swarm (HPSOSSA) algorithm. for improving the cloud computing and Internet of Things (IoT) based task scheduling issue in HCS. The suggested HPSOSSA algorithm finds the best answer to assist HCS customers in completing their medical requests in the shortest amount of time and money by combining the benefits of PSO and SSA.

II. CONCLUSIONS

The cloud computing system has a big user base, and the tasks that users submit are similarly large. The ability to deploy user tasks on the cloud computing system in a fast and acceptable manner is critical since the system must respond to user access requests and submissions at all times. This study proposes a task scheduling technique based on the pheromone factor and its update process in the improved. This study investigates task scheduling in cloud systems to address the issue of slow convergence owing to insufficient initialization. ACO pheromone. The GA-ACO (integration of genetic algorithm with ACO) uses GA's global search capabilities to generate better solutions. These solutions are subsequently turned into the initial pheromone of ACO, leading to optimal scheduling.

III. FUTURE WORK

There is a promising chance to further enhance the performance of ant colony optimization algorithms for cloud computing environments in future study. This may entail fine-tuning parameters, modifying algorithms to fit various cloud configurations, and merging them with additional optimization techniques. Examining how these algorithms scale on different cloud resources while taking into account variables like the quantity of ants, the size of the challenge, and the difficulty of the optimization assignment is another exciting field.

Future investigations could explore combining ACO with deep reinforcement learning for optimizing cloud resource allocation. This entails devising a deep reinforcement learning model capable of learning the best pheromone update approach for ACO in cloud resource allocation.

Another avenue is extending the ACO algorithm to handle multiple objectives in cloud resource allocation, such as optimizing resource utilization, costs, and energy consumption. This would necessitate developing a multi-objective ACO algorithm capable of identifying Pareto-optimal solutions for cloud resource allocation.

Additionally, research could focus on applying ACO to dynamic resource allocation in edge computing, developing an ACO algorithm capable of adjusting to changing resource needs in edge devices and optimizing real-time resource allocation.

Furthermore, exploring the use of ACO in quality of service (QoS) management in cloud computing could be beneficial. This involves creating an ACO algorithm that can optimize QoS parameters like response time, throughput, and availability in cloud computing.

Finally, studying ACO's applicability in fault tolerance and green cloud computing is another promising area. This would involve developing an ACO algorithm that optimizes resource allocation for fault-tolerant and energy-efficient services in cloud computing.

For multi-objective data-intensive service composition in cloud computing, our ACO algorithm appears promising. More research will focus on edge computing dynamic resource allocation, green cloud computing, QoS management, fault tolerance, deep reinforcement learning integration, and improved multi-objective optimization.

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